

MENTORING COMPETENCIES OF MASTER TEACHERS AND PERFORMANCE OF PUBLIC ELEMENTARY TEACHERS IN CLUSTER 8 DIVISION OF CALAMBA CITY

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ABSTRACT

This study examined the mentoring competencies of master teachers and their relationship to the performance of public elementary school teachers in Cluster 8, Division of Calamba City. A descriptive-correlational design was used, with data gathered from 18 master teachers and 123 teachers through simple random sampling. Two questionnaires, one researcher-made and one adopted, served as tools for data collection. Statistical methods included the mean, a four-point Likert scale, independent t-test, and Pearson's r . The findings showed that both master teachers and teachers demonstrated a high level of mentoring competencies. There were no significant differences in their assessments of master teachers' Abilities, Competencies, and Virtues, with p -values of .095, .309, and .768, respectively. Similarly, most areas of teacher performance—such as Diversity of Learners, Learning Environment, Curriculum and Planning, Assessment and Reporting, Community Linkages, and Professional Development—showed no significant differences, with p -values all above .05. However, Content Knowledge and Pedagogy showed a significant difference ($p = .034$). Pearson's correlation revealed a significant positive relationship between mentoring competencies and teacher performance, with correlation values (r) ranging from .364 to .621, indicating low to moderate correlations. All p -values were .000, below the .05 threshold, confirming statistical significance. Based on these findings, a SWOT analysis was proposed to enhance the mentoring competencies of master teachers, recognizing their crucial role in improving teacher performance.

Keywords: *mentoring competencies, master teachers, performance, SWOT analysis*

INTRODUCTION

In a school organization, leadership occurs in various forms and serves multiple purposes. Principals or school heads are portrayed as primary school leaders. However, there are also silent teacher leaders within the school who assist and support the principals in leading the organization and guiding teachers in their teaching practices. They are called master teachers.

Quizada (2023) defined master teachers as independent learners who strove to advance their learning to facilitate successful learning for their students and peers. The primary responsibility of a master teacher was to provide their pupils with access to high-caliber professional competence through mutually beneficial professional development for career teachers.

In addition, these master teachers depicted teacher leadership as they handled a certain group of teachers and provided them with technical assistance for their holistic professional development. According to De Lima (2018, as cited in Quizada 2023), instructional leadership was defined as the ability to involve colleagues collaboratively in mutual learning and development with the main purpose of improving teaching and learning.

Moreover, relevant to instructional leadership was the significant role played by these master teachers, which was to provide mentorship to their colleagues, particularly those under their supervision. One of the key factors in addressing teachers' teaching needs and achieving growth in the professional aspect was mentoring.

Slattery (2020) stated that mentoring was the process by which an expert person facilitated learning in the mentee through arrangements of specific learning experiences Tovey (1999, as cited in Rolfe-Flett 2002). In this case, master teachers were identified as skilled or expert people who could provide learning to the mentees, the teachers.

Ragins et al. (2016, as cited in Ally and Mabagala 2022) mentioned that mentoring programs were important interventions for both novices and experienced teachers as they transmitted skills, experience, and knowledge toward guidance, support, and friendship to the mentees in organizations.

Furthermore, the Department of Education (DepEd) never failed to provide various means to address the teachers' developmental needs. Numerous training and seminars were conducted to fill in the gaps in the teachers' teaching performance. According to Jimenez (2021), teachers attended training and workshops and underwent technical assistance from mentors and experts to be well-equipped for school-related activities, became prepared in teaching, and evolved into holistic developers of the learners.

This was anchored to DepEd Order No. 42, s. 2017 otherwise known as National Adoption and Implementation of the Philippine Professional Standards for Teachers (PPST) where DepEd recognized the importance of professional standards in the continuing professional development and advancement of teachers based on the principle of lifelong learning. The department also adhered to its principle that quality learning is contingent upon quality teaching.

Moreover, PPST contained specific areas that were the basis for improvement in teachers' performance. It had seven domains, namely Content Knowledge and Pedagogy, Learning Environment, Diversity of Learners, Curriculum and Planning, Assessment and Reporting, Community Linkages and Professional Engagement, and Personal Growth and Professional Development. The department ensured that teachers had the necessary skills and knowledge to provide quality education. If a teacher lacked any of these, school heads and master teachers established a mentoring program to support the developmental needs of the teachers.

This study was based on the Triangular Model of Mentor Competence by Johnson which mentioned that the competence of a mentor centers on the presence of virtues, abilities, and micro-skills or competencies.

Ramirez (2012, as cited in Kumar et al. 2024) emphasized that a healthy mentoring relationship was grounded in openness and mentor humility, which could balance the power dynamic. Further, he modified Triangular Model of Mentor Competence in his Article entitled "Intentional Mentor: Effective Mentorship of Undergraduate Science Students". It illustrated virtues from the base of the triangle, which referred to the qualities in an individual regarded as admirable traits that suggested moral and behavioral uprightness. A competent mentor was also caring, exhibiting genuine concern for the mentee, and prudent, demonstrating sound judgment and wisdom.

Furthermore, according to Johnson, abilities were assets not necessarily trainable; however, they were capacities individuals might or might not have as part of their psychological disposition. A mentor was likely to have the intellectual skills necessary to provide a mentee with the instruction needed to make progress in the laboratory or classroom. In addition, the command of emotional and relational elements might be less certain across prospective mentors. As role models in a position to provide counsel, mentors should have been well-balanced emotionally and well-adjusted psychologically.

Johnson also mentioned that competencies was the third side of the triangular model, essentially comprised the fundamental skill set and knowledge that a mentor brought to the mentorship. As opposed to virtues and abilities, mentoring competencies could be readily modified and enhanced through conscious effort. Indeed, it was this aspect of the model in which the intentional mentor could make significant gains in a mentoring relationship.

In addition, this study was anchored with the DepEd Order No. 42, s. 2017, or the Philippine Professional Standards for Teachers (PPST), where the expected

competencies for professional teachers were presented. It included seven domains, namely Content Knowledge and Pedagogy, Learning Environment, Diversity of Learners, Curriculum and Planning, Assessment and Reporting, Community Linkages and Professional Engagement, and Personal Growth and Professional Development. These domains were the basis for DepEd on how to succor the needs of the teachers in terms of professional growth and development.

Ultimately, the purpose of this study was to ascertain the level of mentoring competencies of master teachers and their impact on the performance of public elementary teachers in Cluster 8, Division of Calamba City. This research also aimed to establish a mentoring program to strengthen the mentoring skills of master teachers, which was significant to the progress of the teachers' performance and ultimately beneficial to the learners.

Research Questions

This study determined the relationship between the level of mentoring competencies of master teachers and the performance level of public elementary teachers in Cluster 8, Division of Calamba City. Further, the researcher sought to answer the following questions:

1. What is the level of manifestation of mentoring competencies of master teachers as assessed by master teachers and teachers in terms of:
 - 1.1 Abilities,
 - 1.1.1 Cognitive,
 - 1.1.2 Emotional, and
 - 1.1.3 Relational,
 - 1.2 Competencies,
 - 1.2.1 Student Development,
 - 1.2.2 Relational Phases,
 - 1.2.3 Relationship Structure,
 - 1.2.4 Mentor Functions,
 - 1.2.5 Boundary Maintenance,
 - 1.2.6 Recognizes Dysfunction,
 - 1.2.7 Cross-Gender Skills,
 - 1.2.8 Respect for Autonomy, and
 - 1.2.9 Self-awareness,
 - 1.3 Virtues
 - 1.3.1 Integrity,
 - 1.3.2 Caring, and
 - 1.3.3 Prudence?
2. Is there a significant difference between the assessments of the master teachers and teachers on mentoring competencies of master teachers?
3. What is the performance level of public elementary teachers as assessed by master teachers and teachers in terms of:
 - 3.1 Content Knowledge and Pedagogy,

- 3.2 Diversity of Learners,
 - 3.3 Learning Environment,
 - 3.4 Curriculum and Planning,
 - 3.5 Assessment and Reporting,
 - 3.6 Community Linkages and Professional Engagement, and
 - 3.7 Personal Growth and Professional Development?
4. Is there a significant difference between the assessments of the master teachers and teachers on teachers' performance?
 5. Is there a significant relationship between the master teachers' mentoring competencies level of manifestation and public elementary teachers' performance level?
 6. Based on the findings of the study, what program may be proposed?

METHODOLOGY

This study utilized quantitative research design. Research design, as described by McCombes (2023), was a strategy for answering research questions using empirical data. Specifically, the research methodology of descriptive correlation was employed. Aprecia et al. (2022) stated that a descriptive correlational research design described the variables and measured the extent of the relationships that occurred between and among the variables. The main objective of this study was to identify the level of mentoring competencies of master teachers and determine its relationship to the level of performance of the teachers in Cluster 8, Division of Calamba City.

Furthermore, master teachers and teachers from public elementary schools in Cluster 8, Division of Calamba City, constituted the vital elements of this study's population. Simultaneously, a comprehensive enumeration of schools was achieved. To gather data through sampling, all schools were given an equal opportunity to be selected; therefore, simple random sampling was employed. A simple random sampling was a randomly selected subset of a population. This sampling method involved a single random selection and required minimal advanced knowledge about the population. Due to its use of randomization, any research performed on this sample had high internal and external validity and was at a lower risk of research biases such as sampling bias and selection bias according to Thomas (2023).

Moreover, this study encompassed two sets of variables: the level of manifestation of mentoring competencies of master teachers and the level of public elementary teachers' performance in Cluster 8, Division of Calamba City. The level of mentoring competencies of master teachers included abilities with sub-variables cognitive, emotional, and relational; competencies with sub-variables student development, relational phases, relationship structure, mentor functions, boundary maintenance, recognizing dysfunction, cross-gender skills, respect for autonomy, and self-awareness; and virtues with sub-variables integrity, caring, and prudence. The level of public elementary teachers' performance was based on the seven domains of the Philippine Professional Standards for Teachers, such as Content Knowledge and Pedagogy,

Diversity of Learners, Learning Environment, Curriculum and Planning, Assessment and Reporting, Community Linkages and Professional Engagement, and Personal Growth and Professional Development. This study was limited to the four (4) selected public elementary schools in Cluster 8 Division of Calamba City with eighteen (18) master teachers and one hundred fifty-eight (158) teachers.

A researcher-made questionnaire was formed and utilized as the instrument of the study in determining the level of mentoring competencies of the master teachers, focusing on abilities, competencies, and virtues. This was then measured using a Likert scale with four points: 1 for strongly disagree, 2 for disagree, 3 for agree, and 4 for strongly agree. The weighted mean of each indicator was attained, and the results were averaged to provide a wide assessment and overall findings of the manifestation degree of master teachers' mentoring competencies, which were translated into Verbal and Descriptive Equivalents.

Additionally, this research utilized another set of instruments adapted from the study of Batallones (2023) entitled "New Normal Leadership Skills among School Heads and Philippine Professional Standards for Teachers in Santa Rosa City Private School" to identify the level of performance of public elementary teachers in Cluster 8 Division of Calamba City with the following PPST domains: Content Knowledge and Pedagogy, Learning Environment, Diversity Of Learners, Curriculum and Planning, Assessment and Reporting, Community Linkages and Professional Engagement, and Personal Growth and Professional Development. The Likert scale was used to easily collect responses for the questionnaire's fast distribution, scoring, and evaluation.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Table 1.1

Level of Manifestation of Mentoring Competencies of Master Teachers as assessed by Master Teachers and Teachers in terms of Abilities

Indicators in terms of Abilities	Master Teachers		Teachers		Composite		Rank
	\bar{X}	VI	\bar{X}	VI	\bar{X}	VI	
The master teacher...							
Cognitive Abilities	3.92	FM	3.67	SA	3.79	FM	
1. contributes ideas in crafting the School Improvement Plan (SIP) and Annual Implementation Plan (AIP).	3.84	FM	3.61	SA	3.72	FM	
2. uses variety of teaching techniques, approaches and strategies to make the lesson interesting and meaningful.	3.89	FM	3.65	SA	3.77	FM	1
3. serves as trainer or speaker in school-based INSET and SLAC.	4.00	FM	3.71	SA	3.86	FM	
4. teaches accurate and updated content using appropriate approaches and strategies	3.84	FM	3.67	SA	3.76	FM	

5. aligns lesson objectives, teaching methods, learning activities and instructional strategies.	4.00	FM	3.73	SA	3.86	FM	
Emotional Abilities	3.67	FM	3.56	SA	3.62	FM	
1. is empathetic about someone else's problems.	3.68	FM	3.56	SA	3.62	FM	
2. has control over his or her temper.	3.63	FM	3.49	SA	3.56	FM	
3. show compassion and respect in dealing with peers and superiors.	3.74	FM	3.65	SA	3.69	FM	3
4. describes the ways in which adults identify and solve problems.	3.68	FM	3.54	SA	3.61	FM	
5. mediates with colleagues' conflicts with fairness.	3.63	FM	3.57	SA	3.60	FM	
Relational Abilities	3.73	FM	3.62	SA	3.67	FM	
1. maintains harmonious relationships with colleagues inside and outside workplace.	3.74	FM	3.60	SA	3.67	FM	
2. utilizes active listening skills to improve communication.	3.68	FM	3.66	SA	3.67	FM	
3. demonstrates effective interpersonal relationships with peers and superiors	3.74	FM	3.59	SA	3.66	FM	2
4. builds trust with others by being reliable, honest, and transparent in interactions.	3.74	FM	3.60	SA	3.67	FM	
5. maintains cooperation and collaboration in an effective manner to achieve a common goal.	3.74	FM	3.65	SA	3.69	FM	
GENERAL ASSESSMENT	3.77	FM	3.62	SA	3.67	FM	
Legend: 3.25 – 4.00 Strongly Agree (SA)/ Fully Manifested 1.75 – 2.49 Disagree (D)/ Partially Manifested 2.50 – 3.24 Agree (A)/ Manifested 1.00 – 1.74 Strongly Disagree (SD)/ Not Manifested							

Mentoring Competencies of master teachers in terms of **Abilities** was verbally interpreted as **Fully Manifested (3.67)**. All indicators were verbally interpreted as Fully Manifested. Furthermore, the indicator regarding Cognitive Abilities particularly “The master teacher serves as trainer or speaker in school-based INSET and SLAC” and “The master teacher aligns lesson objectives, teaching methods, learning activities and instructional strategies.” had the highest computed composite mean of **3.86 or Fully Manifested**. Meanwhile, the indicator regarding Emotional Abilities particularly “The master teacher has control over his or her temper.” had the lowest computed composite mean of **3.56 or Fully Manifested**.

This implies that master teachers in public elementary schools in Cluster 8, Division of Calamba City exhibit a high manifestation level of mentoring competencies in terms of abilities. Master teachers' mentoring skills are closely related to their cognitive skills. Their cognitive abilities enable them to assist new colleagues in becoming better educators. They do not merely transfer knowledge; they also demonstrate how to think critically, adjust to changing conditions, and reflect on one's practice in ways that improve both individual teaching effectiveness and overall student outcomes.

Dingal (2023) pointed out that master teachers were leaders who had mastered the basics of teaching, leaders who went above and beyond to ensure a positive learning experience for each student, and leaders who shared their knowledge with the broader learning community. They were expected to have more experience in curriculum development, professional development, and mentoring than a traditional teacher; they

served as role models for all other instructional staff and were considered the "gold standard" in teaching.

Table 1.2

Level of Manifestation of Mentoring Competencies of Master Teachers as assessed by Master Teachers and Teachers in terms of Competencies

Indicators in terms of Competencies	Master Teachers		Teachers		Composite		Rank
	\bar{X}	VI	\bar{X}	VI	\bar{X}	VI	
The master teacher...	\bar{X}	VI	\bar{X}	VI	\bar{X}	VI	
Student Development	3.84	FM	3.70	FM	3.77	FM	
1. stimulates thinking and clarify lessons through effective questions.	3.74	FM	3.66	FM	3.70	FM	
2. is flexible to teaching methods to students' needs, interest and abilities.	3.89	FM	3.74	FM	3.82	FM	
3. uses variety of teaching techniques, approaches and strategies to make the lesson interesting and meaningful.	3.89	FM	3.72	FM	3.81	FM	1.5
4. models in providing appropriate intervention activities for learners at risk.	3.84	FM	3.71	FM	3.78	FM	
5. serves as coach that involve teaching related competitions.	3.84	FM	3.69	FM	3.77	FM	
Relational Phases	3.81	FM	3.65	FM	3.73	FM	
1. establishes good supervisor-subordinate rapport among colleagues.	3.89	FM	3.66	FM	3.78	FM	
2. helps colleagues navigate toward career progression.	3.89	FM	3.65	FM	3.77	FM	
3. establishes rapport among colleagues even outside workplace.	3.79	FM	3.65	FM	3.72	FM	3.5
4. expresses appreciation and gratitude among peers verbally and non-verbally.	3.79	FM	3.68	FM	3.73	FM	
5. serves as a good model to colleagues.	3.68	FM	3.64	FM	3.66	FM	
Relationship Structure	3.79	FM	3.65	FM	3.72	FM	
1. creates a positive working environment that prioritizes colleagues' wellbeing.	3.84	FM	3.64	FM	3.74	FM	
2. promotes harmonious relationships that enhances colleagues' engagement in their work.	3.79	FM	3.68	FM	3.73	FM	5.5
3. keeps colleagues motivated in all aspects.	3.79	FM	3.65	FM	3.72	FM	
4. holds accountable for his or her subordinates in terms of performance level.	3.74	FM	3.65	FM	3.69	FM	
5. serves as a good and reliable leader of the team to abreast teaching.	3.79	FM	3.65	FM	3.72	FM	
6. serves as a good and reliable leader of the team to abreast teaching.	3.79	FM	3.65	FM	3.72	FM	
Mentor Functions	3.84	FM	3.69	FM	3.77	FM	
1. provides technical assistance to colleagues in content and skills difficulties.	3.89	FM	3.70	FM	3.80	FM	1.5
2. conducts echo-seminars for colleagues.	3.84	FM	3.65	FM	3.74	FM	

3. extends TA or coaching to colleagues to improve performance and behavior towards work and mentoring to improve classroom management.	3.89	FM	3.70	FM	3.80	FM	
4. provides guidance and assistance as the novice colleagues assume new roles and responsibilities.	3.79	FM	3.70	FM	3.74	FM	
5. assists principal in instructional monitoring of colleagues.	3.79	FM	3.70	FM	3.75	FM	
Boundary Maintenance	3.67	FM	3.62	FM	3.65	FM	
1. sets limitations in terms of work-related concerns.	3.68	FM	3.61	FM	3.65	FM	
2. delegates tasks among the members of the group or organization to achieve good work dynamics.	3.68	FM	3.68	FM	3.68	FM	
3. prioritizes colleagues' wellbeing in setting work deadlines.	3.68	FM	3.64	FM	3.66	FM	9
4. avoids giving work or tasks to colleagues during rest days and holidays.	3.63	FM	3.54	FM	3.59	FM	
5. maintains professional margins between and among colleagues.	3.68	FM	3.65	FM	3.67	FM	
Recognizes Dysfunctions	3.78	FM	3.65	FM	3.71	FM	
1. addresses issues and concerns professionally.	3.79	FM	3.63	FM	3.71	FM	
2. condones violence, harassment, and bullying within the team.	3.74	FM	3.57	FM	3.65	FM	
3. creates a safe working environment within the organization.	3.79	FM	3.70	FM	3.75	FM	7
4. manifests respect to colleagues beyond their physical limitations.	3.79	FM	3.67	FM	3.73	FM	
5. adapts inclusivity in the workplace.	3.79	FM	3.66	FM	3.72	FM	
Cross Gender Skills	3.78	FM	3.67	FM	3.73	FM	
1. respects individual differences.	3.79	FM	3.70	FM	3.75	FM	
2. honors colleagues' skills and capabilities beyond their gender preferences.	3.74	FM	3.73	FM	3.73	FM	
3. disseminates workloads among the colleagues fairly.	3.74	FM	3.66	FM	3.70	FM	3.5
4. condones discrimination and applies equal treatment.	3.84	FM	3.58	FM	3.71	FM	
5. fosters a culture of security and acceptance.	3.79	FM	3.68	FM	3.73	FM	
Respect for Autonomy	3.76	FM	3.67	FM	3.72	FM	
1. listens to colleagues with empathy.	3.79	FM	3.67	FM	3.73	FM	
2. welcomes complaints as valid.	3.68	FM	3.65	FM	3.67	FM	
3. entertains comments and suggestions from others.	3.68	FM	3.70	FM	3.69	FM	5.5
4. accepts new concepts and ideas from colleagues.	3.79	FM	3.68	FM	3.73	FM	
5. allows colleagues to work at their own pace.	3.84	FM	3.67	FM	3.76	FM	
Self-Awareness	3.68	FM	3.68	FM	3.68	FM	
1. is aware of his or her strengths and weaknesses.	3.63	FM	3.70	FM	3.67	FM	8
2. does his part to improve himself or herself.	3.74	FM	3.70	FM	3.72	FM	
3. presents himself or herself with confidence.	3.74	FM	3.69	FM	3.71	FM	

4. realizes how his or her work role influences others.	3.68	FM	3.66	FM	3.67	FM
5. manifests self-reflection.	3.63	FM	3.64	FM	3.64	FM
GENERAL ASSESSMENT	3.77	FM	3.67	SA	3.72	FM

Legend: 3.25 – 4.00 Strongly Agree (SA)/ Fully Manifested 1.75 – 2.49 Disagree (D)/ Partially Manifested
2.50 – 3.24 Agree (A)/ Manifested 1.00 – 1.74 Strongly Disagree (SD)/ Not Manifested

Mentoring Competencies of master teachers in terms of **Competencies** was verbally interpreted as **Fully Manifested (3.72)**. All indicators were verbally interpreted as Fully Manifested. Moreover, the indicators regarding Student Development and Mentor Functions particularly “The master teacher is flexible to teaching methods to students’ needs, interest and abilities.”, “The master teacher provides technical assistance to colleagues in content and skills difficulties.”, and “The master teacher extends TA or coaching to colleagues to improve performance and behavior towards work and mentoring to improve classroom management.” had the highest computed composite mean of **3.77** or **Fully Manifested**. However, the indicator regarding Boundary Maintenance particularly “The master teacher avoids giving work or tasks to colleagues during rest days and holidays.” had the lowest computed composite mean of **3.60** or **Fully Manifested**.

This implies that master teachers in public elementary schools in Cluster 8, Division of Calamba City display a high level of manifestation of mentoring competencies in terms of student development and mentor functions. Master teachers recognize that learners learn at different paces and in various ways. They adjust their teaching approaches to different learning styles, abilities, and requirements. This includes adjusting the information, methods, or product to the student’s present level of knowledge and offering numerous opportunities for them to interact with the topic.

Acera (2024) stated that master teachers played a critical role in creating a supportive environment for staff members and strengthening their understanding of effective teaching techniques, which improved student outcomes. According to Umaru (2011), as cited in Acera (2024), students’ academic performance benefited from the mentor-guided development of educational materials with characteristics like visibility, simplicity, attractiveness, and clarity.

Table 1.3

Level of Manifestation of Mentoring Competencies of Master Teachers as assessed by Master Teachers and Teachers in terms of Virtues

Indicators in terms of virtues	Master Teachers		Teachers		Composite		Rank
The master teacher...	\bar{X}	VI	\bar{X}	VI	\bar{X}	VI	
Integrity	3.66	FM	3.67	FM	3.67	FM	
1. sets exemplary in the context of professionalism.	3.58	FM	3.69	FM	3.63	FM	1.5

2. manifests honesty and humility always.	3.74	FM	3.62	FM	3.68	FM	
3. maintains stature and behavior that upholds the dignity of teaching.	3.68	FM	3.71	FM	3.70	FM	
4. shows credibility and consistency with decision making and setting of rules and standards.	3.63	FM	3.66	FM	3.64	FM	
5. seeks feedback and accepts criticisms for improvement.	3.68	FM	3.67	FM	3.68	FM	
Caring	3.66	FM	3.68	FM	3.67	FM	
1. demonstrates consideration and patience for colleagues.	3.53	FM	3.63	FM	3.58	FM	
2. displays empathy and kindness.	3.68	FM	3.64	FM	3.66	FM	
3. creates a supportive environment for the team.	3.74	FM	3.69	FM	3.71	FM	1.5
4. approaches issues and concerns positively.	3.74	FM	3.70	FM	3.72	FM	
5. opens his or her line of communication beyond work related concerns.	3.63	FM	3.72	FM	3.68	FM	
Prudence	3.58	FM	3.66	FM	3.62	FM	
1. exhibits a cautious attitude in making decisions to avoid errors.	3.58	FM	3.64	FM	3.61	FM	
2. weighs the foreseen pros and cons of a decision before taking an action.	3.63	FM	3.65	FM	3.64	FM	
3. applies far-sighted, short term, and goal-oriented planning.	3.53	FM	3.68	FM	3.60	FM	3
4. displays careful management of school resources.	3.58	FM	3.66	FM	3.62	FM	
5. leads the team and takes responsibility for his or her actions and considers the potential consequences of their decisions.	3.58	FM	3.66	FM	3.62	FM	
GENERAL ASSESSMENT	3.64	SA	3.67	FM	3.65	FM	

Legend: 3.25 – 4.00 Strongly Agree (SA)/ Fully Manifested 1.75 – 2.49 Disagree (D)/ Partially Manifested
2.50 – 3.24 Agree (A)/ Manifested 1.00 – 1.74 Strongly Disagree (SD)/ Not Manifested

Mentoring Competencies of master teachers in terms of **Virtues** was verbally interpreted as **Fully Manifested (3.65)**. All indicators were verbally interpreted as Fully Manifested. Moreover, the indicators regarding Integrity and Caring particularly “The master teacher maintains stature and behavior that upholds the dignity of teaching.” and “The master teacher approaches issue and concerns positively.” had the highest computed composite mean of **3.67** or **Fully Manifested**. Otherwise, the indicator regarding Prudence particularly “The master teacher applies far-sighted, short term, and goal-oriented planning.” gained the lowest computed composite mean of **3.62** or **Fully Manifested**.

This suggests that master teachers in public elementary schools in Cluster 8, Division of Calamba City demonstrated high level of manifestation of mentoring competencies in terms of virtues. Master teachers continuously display professionalism in all their interactions and decision-making, which helps to preserve the dignity of the teaching profession, ensuring that they demonstrate the greatest levels of professionalism, honesty, and respect in all aspects of their roles.

As stated by Tripathy & Panda (2022), teachers were considered the epitomes of

leaders who embodied the intrinsic characteristics and skills to bring a radical change in society for good. Teachers were interpreted as role models, leaders who, with their unique style, motivated their students and engaged in building their personalities, which played an important role in shaping their careers. Hence, a teacher was considered someone with a marked personality and embedded with several positive attributes.

Table 2

Test of Significant Difference on the Assessment of the Master Teachers and Teachers on Mentoring Competencies of Master Teachers

Sub-variables		Sum of squares	df	Mean square	F Ratio	Sig.	Remarks	Decision
Abilities	Between Groups	.390	1	.390	2.833	.095	Not Significant	Accept H ₀
	Within Groups	19.139	139	.138				
	Total	19.529	140					
Competencies	Between Groups	.188	1	.188	1.044	.309	Not Significant	Accept H ₀
	Within Groups	25.061	139	.180				
	Total	25.250	140					
Virtues	Between Groups	.018	1	.018	.088	.768	Not Significant	Accept H ₀
	Within Groups	29.379	139	.211				
	Total	29.398	140					

Level of significance 0.05

There was no significant difference between the responses of the two groups of respondents on the above-mentioned variables. In the Test of Significant Difference on the Assessment of the master teachers and teachers on mentoring competencies of master teachers as shown in Table 2, the generated computed probability values of Abilities, Competencies, and Virtues were **.095**, **.309**, and **.768** respectively which were greater than the level of significance of 0.05; thus, the null hypothesis is accepted.

This implies that the master teachers and teachers in public elementary schools in Cluster 8, Division of Calamba City share the same perceptions regarding the level of manifestation of mentoring competencies of master teachers in terms of abilities, competencies, and virtues.

The study by Akinola (2021) mentioned that mentoring prospective young professionals provided an opportunity for both the young and the seasoned professionals to develop and refine the necessary skills to be successful in the diverse and rapidly evolving library and information science profession.

According to the study by Echeche (2022), the current trends in education showed that effective coaching and mentoring programs were regarded as a highly effective method of assisting individuals in increasing their self-direction, self-esteem, efficacy, and accomplishments through communication.

Table 3.1

Performance Level of Public Elementary Teachers as assessed by Master Teachers and Teachers in terms of Content Knowledge and Pedagogy

Indicators	Master Teachers		Teachers		Composite		Rank
	\bar{X}	VI	\bar{X}	VI	\bar{X}	VI	
The teacher...							
1. applies knowledge of content within and across curriculum teaching areas.	3.95	VG	3.76	VG	3.85	VG	4
2. uses research-based knowledge and principles of teaching and learning to enhance professional practice.	3.84	VG	3.66	VG	3.75	VG	7
3. ensures the positive use of ICT to facilitate the teaching and learning process.	4.00	VG	3.74	VG	3.87	VG	2
4. uses a range of teaching strategies that enhance learner achievement in literacy and numeracy skills.	3.95	VG	3.80	VG	3.87	VG	2
5. applies a range of teaching strategies to develop critical and creative thinking, as well as other higher-order thinking skills.	3.95	VG	3.74	VG	3.84	VG	5
6. displays proficient use of Mother Tongue, Filipino, and English to facilitate teaching and learning.	3.95	VG	3.79	VG	3.87	VG	2
7. uses effective verbal and non-verbal classroom communication strategies to support learner understanding, participation, engagement, and achievement.	3.89	VG	3.74	VG	3.82	VG	6
GENERAL ASSESSMENT	3.93	VG	3.75	VG	3.84	VG	
Legend: 3.25 – 4.00 Strongly Agree (SA)/ Very Good		1.75 – 2.49 Disagree (D)/ Fair					
2.50 – 3.24 Agree (A)/ Good		1.00 – 1.74 Strongly Disagree (SD)/ Poor					

The public elementary teachers as assessed by master teachers and teachers in terms of **Content Knowledge and Pedagogy** were **Very Good (3.84)**. All indicators were verbally interpreted as Very Good. In addition, the indicators “The teacher ensures the positive use of ICT to facilitate the teaching and learning process.”, “The teacher uses a range of teaching strategies that enhance learner achievement in literacy and numeracy skills.”, and “The teacher displays proficient use of Mother Tongue, Filipino, and English to facilitate teaching and learning.” had the highest computed composite mean of **3.87** or **Very Good**. Meanwhile, the indicator “The teacher uses research-based knowledge and principles of teaching and learning to enhance professional practice.” gained the lowest computed composite mean of **3.75** or **Very Good**.

This implies that teachers in public elementary schools in Cluster 8, Division of Calamba City, have strong performance levels in terms of content knowledge and pedagogy. They are equipped with knowledge and skills in incorporating ICT in classroom settings. Teachers can make classes more engaging and accessible to diverse learning types by incorporating multimedia. This keeps pupils interested and makes learning more accessible. Moreover, this also emphasizes the value of using a variety of effective

teaching approaches to help students improve their skills in these different core areas. Meanwhile, it is proposed that teachers must be equipped with research-based teaching strategies to further promote innovations. By relying on well-established research in education, teachers can improve their teaching methods, increase student engagement, and foster better learning outcomes.

The study by Filgona et al. (2020) claimed that success or failure in the process of teaching a particular concept lay in the pedagogical approach adopted by the teacher, without which the teaching appeared to the students as the deficiencies of the traditional approach, which contrasted with pedagogical knowledge. Actual teaching should not only have contained the teacher’s skillful demonstration of their knowledge but should also have included the ability to guide the students to meaningfully understand the content of the knowledge.

Table 3.2

Performance Level of Public Elementary Teachers as assessed by Master Teachers and Teachers in terms of Diversity of Learners

Indicators	Master Teachers		Teachers		Composite		Rank
	\bar{X}	VI	\bar{X}	VI	\bar{X}	VI	
The teacher...							
1. uses differentiated, developmentally appropriate learning experiences to address learners’ gender, needs, strengths, interests, and experiences.	3.84	VG	3.78	VG	3.81	VG	2.5
2. establishes a learner centered culture by using teaching strategies that respond to their linguistic, cultural, socio-economic and religious backgrounds.	3.84	VG	3.80	VG	3.82	VG	1
3. designs, adapts, and implements teaching strategies that are responsive to learners with disabilities, giftedness and talents.	3.84	VG	3.77	VG	3.81	VG	2.5
4. plans and delivers teaching strategies that are responsive to the special educational needs of the learners in difficult circumstances, including: geographic isolation; chronic illness; displacement due to armed conflict, urban resettlement or disasters; child abuse and child labor practices.	3.74	VG	3.79	VG	3.76	VG	6
5. adapts and uses culturally appropriate teaching strategies to address the needs of learners from indigenous groups.	3.79	VG	3.75	VG	3.77	VG	5
6. manages learner behavior constructively by applying positive and non-violent discipline to ensure learning focused environments.	3.79	VG	3.80	VG	3.80	VG	4
GENERAL ASSESSMENT	3.81	VG	3.78	VG	3.79	VG	

Legend: 3.25 – 4.00 Strongly Agree (SA)/ Very Good
2.50 – 3.24 Agree (A)/ Good

1.75 – 2.49 Disagree (D)/ Fair
1.00 – 1.74 Strongly Disagree (SD)/ Poor

The public elementary teachers as assessed by master teachers and teachers in

terms of **Diversity of Learners** were **Very Good (3.79)**. All indicators were verbally interpreted as Very Good. Furthermore, the indicator “The teacher establishes a learner centered culture by using teaching strategies that respond to their linguistic, cultural, socio-economic and religious backgrounds.” got the highest computed composite mean of **3.82** or **Very Good**, while the indicator “The teacher plans and delivers teaching strategies that are responsive to the special educational needs of the learners in difficult circumstances, including: geographic isolation; chronic illness; displacement due to armed conflict, urban resettlement or disasters; child abuse and child labor practices.” gained the lowest computed composite mean of **3.76** or **Very Good**.

This implies that teachers in public elementary schools in Cluster 8, Division of Calamba City display a strong performance level in terms of diversity of learners. The teachers utilize a learner-centered approach that focuses on students' needs, strengths, and interests, with teaching techniques that adapt to these differences to improve learning outcomes. By creating a learner-centered culture, it fosters a classroom that respects diversity and meets the needs of individual students by utilizing instructional practices that consider their language, cultural, socioeconomic, and religious backgrounds. This method encourages participation, comprehension, and equity, ensuring that every student may succeed in a supportive, inclusive atmosphere.

According to Ruhela (2023), diversity was a multifaceted concept that embraced the multitude of human differences, fostering a more inclusive, equitable, and prosperous society. It was not only a celebration of uniqueness but a recognition of the value that diverse perspectives brought to our world. As we navigated an ever-evolving global landscape, promoting diversity remained an essential endeavor, offering the promise of a brighter and more interconnected future for all.

Table 3.3

Performance Level of Public Elementary Teachers as assessed by Master Teachers and Teachers in terms of Learning Environment

Indicators	Master Teachers		Teachers		Composite		Rank
	\bar{X}	VI	\bar{X}	VI	\bar{X}	VI	
The teacher...							
1. establishes safe and secure learning environments to enhance learning through the consistent implementation of policies, guidelines, and procedure.	3.84	VG	3.80	VG	3.82	VG	2
2. maintains learning environments that promote fairness, respect, and care to encourage learning.	3.84	VG	3.79	VG	3.81	VG	3
3. manages classroom structure to engage learners, individually or in groups, in meaningful exploration, discovery and hands-on activities within a range of physical learning environments.	3.89	VG	3.79	VG	3.84	VG	1
4. maintains supportive learning environments that nurture and inspire learners to participate, cooperate and collaborate in continued learning.	3.74	VG	3.80	VG	3.77	VG	6

5. applies a range of successful strategies that maintain learning environments that motivate learners to work productively by assuming responsibility for their own learning.	3.79	VG	3.78	VG	3.78	VG	4.5
6. manages learner behavior constructively by applying positive and non-violent discipline to ensure learning focused environments.	3.79	VG	3.78	VG	3.78	VG	4.5
GENERAL ASSESSMENT	3.82	VG	3.79	VG	3.80	VG	
Legend: 3.25 – 4.00 Strongly Agree (SA)/ Very Good	1.75 – 2.49 Disagree (D)/ Fair						
2.50 – 3.24 Agree (A)/ Good	1.00 – 1.74 Strongly Disagree (SD)/ Poor						

The public elementary teachers as assessed by master teachers and teachers in terms of **Learning Environment** were **Very Good (3.80)**. All indicators were verbally interpreted as Strongly Agree or Very Good. In addition, the indicator “The teacher manages classroom structure to engage learners, individually or in groups, in meaningful exploration, discovery and hands-on activities within a range of physical learning environments.” got the highest computed composite mean of **3.84** or **Very Good**, however the indicator “The teacher maintains supportive learning environments that nurture and inspire learners to participate, cooperate and collaborate in continued learning.” garnered the lowest computed composite mean of **3.77** or **Very Good**.

This highlights that teachers in public elementary schools in Cluster 8, Division of Calamba City exhibited a strong performance level in terms of learning environment. They create and utilize a well-organized and adaptable classroom setup that promotes active and student-centered learning. In such an environment, learners are encouraged to engage in investigation, problem-solving, and hands-on activities that enhance deeper learning and a variety of abilities.

According to Ryan & Deci (2016), as cited in Dalimunthe (2024), a conducive and supportive learning environment had a very important role in increasing student motivation and involvement in the learning process. When students were in an environment that facilitated learning well, they tended to feel more motivated and actively involved in learning activities. This allowed students to feel more confident and encouraged to take part in the learning process,

Table 3.4

Performance Level of Public Elementary Teachers as assessed by Master Teachers and Teachers in terms of Curriculum and Planning

Indicators	Master Teachers		Teachers		Composite		Rank
	\bar{X}	VI	\bar{X}	VI	\bar{X}	VI	
The teacher...							
1. plans, manages, and implements developmentally sequenced teaching and learning processes to meet curriculum requirements and varied teaching contexts.	3.84	VG	3.75	SA	3.79	VG	2

2. sets achievable and appropriate learning outcomes that are aligned with learning competencies.	3.79	VG	3.75	SA	3.77	VG	3.5
3. adapts and implements learning programs that ensure relevance and responsiveness to the needs of all learners.	3.95	VG	3.73	SA	3.84	VG	1
4. participates in collegial discussions that use teacher and learners feedback to enrich teaching practice.	3.79	VG	3.75	SA	3.77	VG	3.5
5. selects, develops, organizes, and uses appropriate teaching and learning resources, including ICT, to address learning goals.	3.79	VG	3.74	SA	3.76	VG	5
GENERAL ASSESSMENT	3.83	VG	3.74	SA	3.79	VG	
Legend: 3.25 – 4.00 Strongly Agree (SA)/ Very Good	1.75 – 2.49 Disagree (D)/ Fair						
2.50 – 3.24 Agree (A)/ Good	1.00 – 1.74 Strongly Disagree (SD)/ Poor						

The public elementary teachers as assessed by master teachers and teachers in terms of **Curriculum and Planning** were **Very Good (3.79)**. All indicators were verbally interpreted as Very Good. Additionally, the indicator “The teacher adapts and implements learning programs that ensure relevance and responsiveness to the needs of all learners.” garnered the highest computed composite mean of **3.84** or **Very Good**. On the other hand, the indicator “The teacher selects, develops, organizes, and uses appropriate teaching and learning resources, including ICT, to address learning goals.” got the lowest computed composite mean of **3.76** or **Very Good**.

This implies that teachers in public elementary schools in Cluster 8, Division of Calamba City demonstrate a strong performance level in terms of curriculum and planning. Teachers develop and execute learning programs that are sensitive to the requirements of all learners which demand adaptability, inventiveness, and a thorough grasp of each student's strengths, problems, and interests. Differentiating instruction, using culturally sensitive approaches, and making learning relevant to real-world concerns help teachers guarantee that their classes are meaningful and engaging for all students. However, this also underscores the relevance of resource management in effective teaching. Teachers must carefully select, design, and organize a wide range of resources to help students engage and achieve learning objectives. This method necessitates the deliberate selection of materials that are linked with curriculum goals, as well as the appropriate use of technology to maximize learning opportunities.

Thero (2024) stated that effective curriculum planning ensured clarity of purpose and consistency, facilitating focused learning and skill development. It promoted inclusiveness and cultural relevance, addressing the diverse backgrounds and experiences of students. Additionally, it established a mechanism for continuous improvement, incorporating feedback and fostering innovation. Efficient resource management and teacher preparedness were also key benefits of strategic curriculum planning. By setting clear standards and benchmarks, it ensured accountability and provided a framework for evaluating educational effectiveness. Ultimately, curriculum planning prepared students for future careers and lifelong learning, aligning education with the evolving demands of society.

Table 3.5

Performance Level of Public Elementary Teachers as assessed by Master Teachers and Teachers in terms of Assessment and Reporting

Indicators	Master Teachers		Teachers		Composite		Rank
	\bar{X}	VI	\bar{X}	VI	\bar{X}	VI	
The teacher...							
1. designs, selects, organizes, and uses diagnostic, formative and summative assessment strategies consistent with curriculum requirements.	3.84	VG	3.76	SA	3.80	VG	2.5
2. monitors and evaluates learner progress and achievement using learner attainment data.	3.84	VG	3.80	SA	3.82	VG	1
3. uses strategies for providing timely, accurate and constructive feedback to improve learner performance.	3.79	VG	3.78	SA	3.78	VG	4.5
4. communicates promptly and clearly the learners' needs, progress and achievement to key stakeholders, including parents/guardians.	3.74	VG	3.83	SA	3.78	VG	4.5
5. utilizes assessment data to inform the modification of teaching and learning practices and programs.	3.84	VG	3.76	SA	3.80	VG	2.5
GENERAL ASSESSMENT	3.81	VG	3.79	SA	3.80	VG	
Legend: 3.25 – 4.00 Strongly Agree (SA)/ Very Good		1.75 – 2.49 Disagree (D)/ Fair					
2.50 – 3.24 Agree (A)/ Good		1.00 – 1.74 Strongly Disagree (SD)/ Poor					

The public elementary teachers as assessed by master teachers and teachers in terms of **Assessment and Reporting** were **Very Good (3.80)**. All indicators were verbally interpreted as Very Good. Moreover, the indicator “The teacher monitors and evaluates learner progress and achievement using learner attainment data.” gained the highest computed composite mean of **3.82** or **Very Good**, while the indicators “The teacher uses strategies for providing timely, accurate and constructive feedback to improve learner performance.” and “The teacher communicates promptly and clearly the learners’ needs, progress and achievement to key stakeholders, including parents/guardians.” had the lowest computed composite mean of **3.78** or **Very Good**.

This suggests that those teachers in public elementary schools in Cluster 8, Division of Calamba City demonstrate a strong performance level in assessment and reporting. Monitoring and analyzing learner progress using attainment data is an effective technique for teachers to ensure that pupils are making significant progress toward their learning objectives. Teachers can provide support to each student by collecting and evaluating data from formative and summative exams, identifying trends and patterns, and altering teaching tactics. Frequent and constructive feedback, combined with differentiated instruction, ensures that all students are engaged and challenged at their level. When data is used intentionally and reflectively, it results in better learning outcomes, more student engagement, and a more tailored learning experience for each learner.

On the other hand, this also implied that creating a harmonious relationship with stakeholders particularly, the parents, is also an effective tool to provide learners with the education they deserve. By regularly sharing clear, accurate, and constructive updates on a student’s needs, progress, and achievement, teachers can ensure that parents are informed and involved. Communication should be timely, respectful, and solution-focused, particularly when addressing concerns.

Shuanghong, et al. (2022) emphasized that student progress was of great significance for teachers and students to adjust teaching and learning strategies. In contrast to mastery measurement, which told whether a student had understood the knowledge concepts, monitoring student progress could evaluate the effectiveness of the teaching strategy, and teachers could promptly adjust instruction if the rate at which a specific student was learning seemed insufficient.

Table 3.6

Performance Level of Public Elementary Teachers as assessed by Master Teachers and Teachers in terms of Community Linkages and Professional Engagement

Indicators	Master Teachers		Teachers		Composite		Rank
	\bar{X}	VI	\bar{X}	VI	\bar{X}	VI	
The teacher...							
1. maintains learning environments that are responsive to community contexts.	3.84	VG	3.79	SA	3.81	VG	1
2. builds relationships with parents/guardians and the wider school community to facilitate involvement in the educative process.	3.84	VG	3.75	SA	3.80	VG	2.5
3. reviews regularly personal teaching practice using existing laws and regulations that apply to the teaching profession and the responsibilities specified in the code of ethics for professional teachers.	3.84	VG	3.76	SA	3.80	VG	2.5
4. complies with and implements school policies and procedures consistently to foster harmonious relationships with learners, parents, and other stakeholders.	3.74	VG	3.75	SA	3.74	VG	4
GENERAL ASSESSMENT	3.82	VG	3.76	SA	3.79	VG	

Legend: 3.25 – 4.00 Strongly Agree (SA)/ Very Good
 2.50 – 3.24 Agree (A)/ Good
 1.75 – 2.49 Disagree (D)/ Fair
 1.00 – 1.74 Strongly Disagree (SD)/ Poor

The public elementary teachers as assessed by master teachers and teachers in terms of **Community Linkages and Professional Engagement** were **Very Good (3.79)**. All indicators were verbally interpreted as Very Good. Further, the indicator “The teacher maintains learning environments that are responsive to community contexts.” accumulated the highest computed composite mean of **3.81** or **Very Good**. Meanwhile, the indicator “The teacher complies with and implements school policies and procedures consistently to foster harmonious relationships with learners, parents, and other stakeholders.” got the lowest computed composite mean of **3.74** or **Very Good**.

Teachers in public elementary schools in Cluster 8, Division of Calamba City

manifested a strong performance level in terms of community linkages and professional engagement. Teachers who understand their students' social, cultural, economic, and historical backgrounds can design more relevant, engaging, and successful learning environments that represent the community's variety and values. A learning environment that responds to community circumstances ensures that all students feel noticed, appreciated, and connected to their education. A community-responsive classroom also supports students' emotional well-being and encourages active participation in local life, fostering a sense of belonging and social responsibility.

However, this also highlights the need to improve the teacher's knowledge and skills in complying with implemented school policies. When teachers adhere to established policies and processes, they not only ensure the school's efficiency but also foster a sense of confidence and consistency among students, parents, and stakeholders. This consistency is essential for creating a friendly and professional environment in which everyone, including students, parents, and colleagues, feels appreciated and valued.

In connection to this, in the study of Kabesa and Okioma (2019, as cited in Herrera 2024), the fact that existing programs and initiatives subscribed to the idea that the school's immediate community, including the school's linkages and partners, was a wonderful curriculum laboratory that provided learning opportunities for students and could indeed enhance teaching-learning.

Table 3.7

Performance Level of Public Elementary Teachers as assessed by Master Teachers and Teachers in terms of Personal Growth and Professional Development

Indicators	Master Teachers		Teachers		Composite		Rank
	\bar{X}	VI	\bar{X}	VI	\bar{X}	VI	
The teacher...							
1. applies a personal philosophy of teaching that is learner centered.	3.74	VG	3.79	SA	3.76	VG	5
2. adopts practices that uphold the dignity of teaching as a profession by exhibiting qualities such as caring attitude, respect, and integrity.	3.89	VG	3.80	SA	3.84	VG	1
3. participates in professional networks to share knowledge and to enhance practice.	3.84	VG	3.79	SA	3.81	VG	2
4. develops a personal professional improvement plan based on reflection of one's practice and ongoing professional learning.	3.84	VG	3.75	SA	3.79	VG	3
5. sets professional development goals based on the Philippine Professional Standards for Standards.	3.79	VG	3.78	SA	3.78	VG	4
GENERAL ASSESSMENT	3.82	VG	3.78	SA	3.80	VG	

Legend: 3.25 – 4.00 Strongly Agree (SA)/ Very Good
2.50 – 3.24 Agree (A)/ Good

1.75 – 2.49 Disagree (D)/ Fair
1.00 – 1.74 Strongly Disagree (SD)/ Poor

The public elementary teachers as assessed by master teachers and teachers in terms of **Personal Growth and Professional Development** were **Very Good (3.80)**. All

indicators were verbally interpreted as Strongly Agree or Very Good. In addition, the indicator “The teacher adopts practices that uphold the dignity of teaching as a profession by exhibiting qualities such as caring attitude, respect, and integrity.” gained the highest computed composite mean of **3.84** or **Very Good**. On the other hand, the indicator “The teacher applies a personal philosophy of teaching that is learner-centered.” garnered the lowest computed composite mean of **3.76** or **Very Good**.

Teachers in public elementary schools in Cluster 8, Division of Calamba City established a strong performance level in terms of personal growth and professional development. Teachers manifest the essential principles that contribute to the professionalism and ethical standards that educators are supposed to maintain. Teachers are accountable not only to convey knowledge but also to create a pleasant learning environment that respects the teaching profession and models appropriate behavior for their pupils. Meanwhile, it also underscores the importance of a teaching principle that prioritizes the needs, interests, and learning styles of students. Applying a learner-centered philosophy means designing teaching practices that prioritize the needs and engagement of students.

Damirchi (2024) mentioned that as role models, teachers had to follow a professional code of ethics. This ensured that students received a fair, honest, and uncompromising education. A professional code of ethics outlined teachers’ main responsibilities to the students and defined their role in students’ lives. Above all, teachers had to demonstrate integrity, impartiality, and ethical behavior in the classroom and their conduct with parents and coworkers.

Table 4

The Test of Significant Difference on the Assessment of the Master Teachers and Teachers on Teachers’ Performance

Sub-variables		Sum of squares	df	Mean square	F Ratio	Sig.	Remarks	Decision
Content Knowledge and Pedagogy	Between Groups	.573	1					
	Within Groups	17.429	139	.573	4.571	.034	Significant	Reject H ₀
	Total	18.003	140	.125				
Diversity of Learners	Between Groups	.013	1	.013				
	Within Groups	19.938	139	.143				
	Total	19.951	140					
Learning Environment	Between Groups	.011	1	.011	.070	.791	Not Significant	Accept H ₀
	Within Groups	21.063	139	.152				
	Total	21.074	140					
Curriculum and Planning	Between Groups	.130	1	.130	.857	.356	Not Significant	Accept H ₀
	Within Groups	21.099	139	.152				
	Total	21.230	140					

Assessment and Reporting	Between Groups	.011	1	.011	.076	.783	Not Significant	Accept H _o
	Within Groups	19.171	139	.138				
	Total	19.182	140					
Community Linkages and Professional Engagement	Between Groups	.047	1	.047	.316	.575	Not Significant	Accept H _o
	Within Groups	20.712	139	.149				
	Total	20.759	140					
Personal Growth and Professional Development	Between Groups	.030	1	.030	.212	.646	Not Significant	Accept H _o
	Within Groups	19.336	139	.139				
	Total	19.366	140					

Level of significance 0.05

There was no significant difference between the responses of the two groups of respondents on the above-mentioned variables. In the Test of Significant Difference on the assessment of the master teachers and teachers on performance level of public elementary teachers in Cluster 8, Division of Calamba City as shown in Table 4, the generated computed probability values of Diversity of Learners, Learning Environment, Curriculum and Planning, Assessment and Reporting, Community Linkages and Professional Engagement, and Personal Growth and Professional Development were **.767**, **.791**, **.356**, **.783**, **.575**, and **.646** respectively which were greater than the level of significance of 0.05; thus accepting the null hypothesis.

However, there was a significant difference between the assessments of master teachers and teachers on the performance level of public elementary teachers in Cluster 8, Division of Calamba City on Content Knowledge and Pedagogy. The probability value was **.034** which was less than the level of significance of 0.05; thus, rejecting the null hypothesis.

This indicates that the master teachers and public elementary teachers in Cluster 8, Division of Calamba City have a similar assessment of the performance level of teachers in terms of Diversity of Learners, Learning Environment, Curriculum and Planning, Assessment and Reporting, Community Linkages and Professional Engagement, and Personal Growth and Professional Development. This also points to the possibility that master teachers and teachers may have different perspectives on Content Knowledge and Pedagogy, suggesting that there is a need to improve this performance indicator for the teachers. Improving these areas entails both strengthening one's understanding of the subject matter (content knowledge) and honing the methods and strategies utilized to teach that topic (pedagogy). Both areas are interdependent: good topic understanding improves the ability to teach successfully, whereas excellent pedagogy makes complicated content more accessible to students. Addressing this may lead to better performance for the public elementary teachers in Cluster 8, Division of Calamba City.

To support this, Chieng (2024) believed that the effectiveness of providing high-quality education was increased as a direct result of the master teachers' instructional

leadership; they served as the compass in this process. To overcome the learning gap that the pandemic caused in the students, the master teachers carried out their duties.

As a result, Arche (2022) stated that whatever the teacher did, the learning processes changed, influencing the way students learned. A performing teacher created an achieving student depending on the kind of performance the teacher was demonstrating in terms of how one utilized competence or showed personality.

With this, Tantawy (2020) emphasized that school leaders continually strived to bring about and implement the best educational practices, and professional development was the main strategy through which school systems bolstered teachers' performance levels.

Table 5

Test of Significant Relationship between the Master Teachers' Mentoring Competencies Level of Manifestation and Public Elementary Teachers' Performance Level

master teachers' mentoring competencies level	public elementary teachers' performance level	r value	P value	Remarks	Decision
Abilities	Content Knowledge and Pedagogy	.364**	.000	Significant	Reject H ₀
	Diversity of Learners	.456**	.000	Significant	Reject H ₀
	Learning Environment	.441**	.000	Significant	Reject H ₀
	Curriculum and Planning	.442**	.000	Significant	Reject H ₀
	Assessment and Reporting	.443**	.000	Significant	Reject H ₀
	Community Linkages and Professional Engagement	.525**	.000	Significant	Reject H ₀
	Personal Growth and Professional Development	.493**	.000	Significant	Reject H ₀
Competencies	Content Knowledge and Pedagogy	.522**	.000	Significant	Reject H ₀
	Diversity of Learners	.585**	.000	Significant	Reject H ₀
	Learning Environment	.578**	.000	Significant	Reject H ₀
	Curriculum and Planning	.561**	.000	Significant	Reject H ₀
	Assessment and Reporting	.572**	.000	Significant	Reject H ₀
	Community Linkages and Professional Engagement	.602**	.000	Significant	Reject H ₀
	Personal Growth and Professional Development	.621**	.000	Significant	Reject H ₀
Virtues	Content Knowledge and Pedagogy	.607**	.000	Significant	Reject H ₀
	Diversity of Learners	.592**	.000	Significant	Reject H ₀
	Learning Environment	.555**	.000	Significant	Reject H ₀
	Curriculum and Planning	.564**	.000	Significant	Reject H ₀
	Assessment and Reporting	.553**	.000	Significant	Reject H ₀
	Community Linkages and Professional Engagement	.585**	.000	Significant	Reject H ₀
	Personal Growth and Professional Development	.571**	.000	Significant	Reject H ₀

**Correlational at the level 0.01

*Correlational at the level 0.05(Two-tailed)

The result showed that there was a significant relationship between the independent and dependent variables. In the Test of Significant Relationship between the master teachers' mentoring competencies level of manifestation and public elementary

teachers' performance level, the r values ranging from .364 to .621 were interpreted as with low positive correlation to moderate positive correlation as to correlate master teachers' mentoring competencies level and public elementary teachers' performance level. The computed probability values .000 were lesser than the level of significant ($P < 0.05$); thus, the null hypothesis is rejected.

This implies that master teachers' mentoring competencies level of manifestation has a significant relationship with public elementary teachers' performance level. The higher the master teachers' mentoring competencies level of manifestation, the higher the public elementary teachers' performance level.

Archibong (2012, as cited by Tinaytina 2022), mentioned that mentors, as instructional frontrunners, found means to support their co-teachers in carrying out their duties and responsibilities in aiding students' knowledge and understanding through efficient lesson plans of activities and suitable, sufficient, and modernized instructional materials.

In addition, according to Umaru (2011, as cited in Tinaytina 2022), when mentees were nurtured and directed by their mentors in producing IMs that possessed characteristics of visibility, simplicity, attraction, and clarity, it influenced students' academic performance.

However, based on the study of Chieng (2024), when teachers were not well supervised, effectiveness in instruction was adversely affected and the instructional purposes were not well realized. Thus, this only meant that Master Teachers' instructional leadership had to be properly employed to address the current situation.

Table 6

The Proposed Program

“Strategic Insights: Evaluating Mentoring Competencies and Teacher Performance”

CATEGORIES	STRENGTHS	WEAKNESSES	REMARKS	ACTIVITIES
Mentoring Competencies of Master Teachers	Emotional Skills			
	Empathy towards students and colleagues	Potential for emotional burnt-out	Master teachers excel in emotional skills but need to manage their well-being effectively.	Participate in emotional intelligence workshops

Performance of Teachers	Boundary Maintenance	Clear understanding of professional boundaries	Difficulty balancing approachability and authority	Master teachers maintain boundaries well but need to balance flexibility and approachability.	Attend boundary-setting seminars
	Prudence	Efficient in setting and achieving short-term objectives.	May prioritize short-term gains over long-term benefits	Master teachers are effective in short-term planning but need to ensure alignment with long-term goals.	Use short-term planning to support long-term objectives
	Research-Based Teaching Strategies	Evidence-based approach enhances teaching effectiveness	Potential resistance to change from traditional practices	Teachers effectively use research-based strategies to improve student outcomes but may face resistance and time constraints.	Collaborate with peers to share and update strategies
	Learners with Special Needs	Implementation of inclusive teaching methods	Potential lack of training in special education	Teachers effectively use tailored strategies to support learners with special needs but may face resource and training challenges.	Collaborate with special education professionals to enhance support
	Supportive Environment	Positive classroom climate that encourages student participation	May struggle with large class sizes	Teachers excel in fostering a supportive learning environment but may face challenges with larger classes.	Implement small group activities
	Resource Management of Teachers	Efficient use of available resources	Limited budget constraints	Teachers effectively manage resources but face budgetary and distribution challenges.	Collaborate with administration for better resource allocation

Communication with Parents	Regular parent-teacher conferences	Potential for miscommunication	Effective parent-teacher communication, though engagement levels and miscommunication can be challenges.	Provide clear and concise communication channels
Personal Teaching Practices	Adaptability to different learning styles	Potential for inconsistent practices	Teachers demonstrate strong instructional techniques but need to ensure consistency and personalized feedback.	Implement peer observations for constructive feedback
Philosophy in Teaching	Consistency in teaching approach	May limit flexibility in diverse classrooms	A clear teaching philosophy provides consistency but must adapt to meet diverse student needs.	Regularly review and reflect on teaching philosophy

Based on the comprehensive review of the mentoring competencies of master teachers and the performance of the teachers and indicators with the lowest means, an output below was proposed.

This SWOT Analysis, entitled Strategic Insights: Evaluating Mentoring Competencies and Teacher Performance, aimed to thoroughly examine the mentoring capabilities of master teachers and the teaching performance of public elementary teachers, identifying their strengths and weaknesses, accompanied by remarks and activities. By obtaining strategic insights, this analysis aimed to create targeted improvement strategies that would enhance mentorship practices and overall teaching effectiveness. Ultimately, the goal was to elevate educational outcomes, fostering a supportive and high-performing learning environment for both teachers and students.

Conclusions

Based on the findings of the study, the following conclusions arrived:

1. That the master teachers in public elementary schools in Cluster 8, Division of Calamba City exhibit high level of manifestation of mentoring competencies. This high level of mentoring competencies implies that these master teachers possess the requisite skills, knowledge, and attributes that significantly contribute to the professional development and performance of their colleagues.

2. That the master teachers and public elementary teachers in Cluster 8, Division of Calamba City share the same perceptions regarding the manifestation level of mentoring competencies of master teachers. This shared perception underscores a

consistent understanding and recognition of the pivotal role master teachers play in the educational landscape of this division.

3. That the public elementary teachers in Cluster 8, Division of Calamba City demonstrate strong performance level. This comprehensive evaluation highlights the multifaceted competencies of these educators, reflecting their commitment to excellence and continuous improvement in their professional practice.

4. That the master teachers and public elementary teachers in Cluster 8, Division of Calamba City have the same assessments regarding the performance level of teachers in terms of Diversity of Learners, Learning Environment, Curriculum and Planning, Assessment and Reporting, Community Linkages and Professional Engagement, and Personal Growth and Professional Development. However, they differ on their perceptions in terms of Content Knowledge and Pedagogy. The convergence and divergence in their perceptions provide valuable insights into the strengths and areas for potential improvement within the educational community.

5. That the master teachers' mentoring competencies level of manifestation have direct connection on the performance level of public elementary teachers in Cluster 8, Division of Calamba City. The higher the master teachers' mentoring competencies level of manifestation, the higher the public elementary teachers' performance level. This relationship underscores the vital role that master teachers play in shaping the educational landscape and enhancing the overall quality of teaching within and outside the school.

6. That the proposed program entitled "Strategic Insights: Evaluating Mentoring Competencies and Teacher Performance" can be adapted to equip master teachers in providing mentoring, coaching, and technical assistance among teachers and improve their performance level holistically.

Recommendations

Based on the summarized findings of the study and finalized conclusions, the following recommendations are highly encouraged:

1. To sustain and improve the mentoring skills of master teachers in public elementary schools in Cluster 8, the administration may provide professional development programs tailored to enhance the skills of master teachers in mentoring through various specialized training or mentoring workshops which can help them to further develop the required abilities and competencies.

2. To improve the mentor-mentee relationship of master teachers and teachers in public elementary schools in Cluster 8, school heads may foster a culture of trust and mutual respect, encourage open communication, build emotional support and encouragement, and create opportunities for mentees to lead. Setting clear goals and expectations and celebrating mentoring relationships may lead to positive feedback loop

and reinforce the importance of the mentoring process.

3. To enhance the performance level of teachers in public elementary school teachers in Cluster 8, school heads, master teachers, and teachers may design continuous, job-embedded professional development that is aligned to the teachers' needs and the specific context of the school. Schools may also sustain the implementation of an established system of regular classroom observations where administrators, senior teachers, or peers observe teaching practices and provide constructive feedback.

4. To enhance the performance level of teachers in public elementary school teachers in Cluster 8, master teachers, as teacher leaders, may establish a structured and well-defined mentoring program suitable to the needs of the teachers, provided with clear goals and objectives, targeted professional development, and constructive feedback and guidance.

5. To strengthen the relationship between the mentoring skills of master teachers and the performance level of teachers, administration may provide comprehensive training, regular feedback, professional development, supportive environments, and adequate resources appropriate to the two parties' individual needs.

6. Public elementary schools in Cluster 8, Division of Calamba City may adapt the program of this study called "Strategic Insights: Evaluating Mentoring Competencies and Teacher Performance" to serve as a guide for the school heads and master teachers to assist and address the developmental needs of the teachers and improve the quality of their performance level as educators which drive complete development.

7. Future researchers may use the findings, conclusions, and recommendations of this study to further explore on enhancing the significant competencies of school leaders, including master teachers, as well as their impact to teachers' professional development as this could yield valuable insights for policy improvements within Calamba City.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

The author declares that there are no financial, personal, or professional interests that could be perceived as influencing the research or its interpretation. No competing interests are present that would affect the objectivity, integrity, or impartiality of the study or its findings. The author confirms that all aspects of the research were conducted without any potential conflict of interest.

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